

UNIVERSITE DE YAOUNDE I

FACULTE DE MEDECINE ET DES
SCIENCES BIOMEDICALES

ECOLE DOCTORALE
SCIENCE DE LA VIE, SANTE ET
ENVIRONNEMENT

MASTER PROFESSIONNEL

SANTE DU TRAVAIL

THE UNIVERSITY OF YAOUNDE I

FACULTY OF MEDICINE AND
BIOMEDICAL SCIENCES

GRADUATE PROGRAMME LIFE
SCIENCES, HEALTH AND
ENVIRONMENT

PROFESSIONAL MASTERS
PROGRAM

OCCUPATIONAL HEALTH

TEACHERS EXPERIENCES OF WORK PLACE VIOLENCE AND HARASSMENT COMMITTED BY LEARNERS IN SECONDARY SCHOOLS IN YAOUNDE VII

Thesis written in partial fulfilments of the requirements for the award of a
professional Master's Degree.

Option: Occupational Health

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School year: 2023-2024

DEDICATION

I dedicate this work to all the diligent and devoted teachers who face a growing challenge of violence at work while trying to educate the next generation. Despite the challenges your job ignites imagination, instills love of learning and inspires for a hope of a better tomorrow. Thank you!

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20	JEMEA Bonaventure	AP	Anesthesiology – Intensive care
21	NGO YAMBEN Marie Ange	AP	Orthopedic Surgery
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30	IROUME Cristella Raïssa BIFOUNA épouse NTYO'O NKOUMOU	L	Anesthesiology – Intensive care
31	KONA NGONDO François Stéphane	L	Anesthesiology – Intensive care
32	MBOUCHE Landry Oriole	L	Urology
33	MEKEME MEKEME Junior Barthelemy	L	Urology
34	MULUEM Olivier Kennedy	L	Orthopedic Surgery - traumatology
35	NWAHA MAKON Axel Stéphane	L	Urology
36	NDIKONTAR KWANJI Raymond	L	Anesthesiology – Intensive care

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38	NYANIT BOB Dorcas	L	Pediatric Surgery
39	SAVOM Eric Patrick	L	General Surgery
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44	KINGUE Samuel	P	Internal Medicine /Cardiology
45	KUATE TEGUEU Calixte	P	Internal Medicine /Nephrology
46	MBANYA Jean Claude	P	Internal Medicine /Endocrinology
47	NDJITTOYAP NDAM Elie Claude	P	Internal Medicine /Hepato- Gastroenterology
48	NDOM Paul	P	Internal Medicine /Oncology
49	NJAMNSHI Alfred K.	P	Internal Medicine /Neurology
50	NOUEDOUI Christophe	P	Internal Medicine /Endocrinology
51	SINGWE Madeleine épouse NGANDEU	P	Internal Medicine /Rheumatology
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56	HAMADOU BA	SL	Internal Medicine /Cardiology
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61	NDONGO AMOUGOU Sylvie	SL	Internal Medicine /Cardiology
62	BOOMBHI Jérôme	SL	Internal Medicine /Cardiology
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64	NGANOU Chris Nadège	SL	Internal Medicine /Cardiology
65	KAMGA OLEN Jean Pierre Olivier	L	Internal Medicine /Cardiology
66	NTONE ENYIME Félicien	L	Internal Medicine /Psychiatry
67	ZE Jean Jacques	L	Internal Medicine /Pneumology
68	ANABA MELINGUI Victor Yves	L	Internal Medicine /Rhyematology
69	ATENGUENA OBALEMBA Etienne	L	Internal Medicine /Medical Cancerology
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97	MBOUDOU Émile	P	Gynecology/Obstetrics	
98	MBU ENOW Robinson	P	Gynecology/Obstetrics	
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106	NOA NDOUA Claude Cyrille	AP	Gynecology/Obstetrics	
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111	MENDOUA Michèle Florence épouse NKODO	L	Gynecology/Obstetrics
112	METOGO NTSAMA Junie Annick	L	Gynecology/Obstetrics
113	NSAHLAI Christiane JIVIR FOMU	L	Gynecology/Obstetrics
114	NYADA Serge Robert	L	Gynecology/Obstetrics
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126	KAGMENI Gilles	AP	Ophtalmology
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131	ANDJOCK NKOUO Yves Christian	L	ENT
132	ASMAOU BOUBA Dalil	L	ENT
133	ATANGA Léonel Christophe	L	ENT/CFS
134	BOLA SIAFA Antoine	L	ENT
135	MEVA'A BIOUELE Roger Christian	L	ENT/CFS
136	MOSSUS Yannick	L	ENT/CFS
137	MVILONGO TSIMI épouse BENGONO Caroline	L	Ophtalmology
138	NANFACK NGOUNE Chantal	L	Ophtalmology
139	NGO NYEKI Adèle-Rose épouse MOUAHA-BELL	L	ENT/CFS
140	NOMO Arlette Francine	L	Ophtalmology
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142	KOKI NDOMBO Paul	P	Pediatrics
143	ABENA OBAMA Marie Thérèse	P	Pediatrics
144	CHIABI Andreas	P	Pediatrics
145	CHELO David	P	Pediatrics
146	NGUEFACK Séraphin	P	Pediatrics

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147	MBASSI AWA	AP	Pediatrics
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150	NGUEFACK épouse DONGMO Félicitée	AP	Pediatrics
151	ONGOTSOYI Angèle H.	AP	Pediatrics
152	KALLA Ginette Claude épouse MBOPI KEOU	SL	Pediatrics
153	NOUBI N. épouse KAMGAING M.	SL	Pediatrics
154	EPEE épouse NGOUE Jeannette	L	Pediatrics
155	KAGO TAGUE Daniel Armand	L	Pediatrics
156	MEGUIEZE Claude-Audrey	L	Pediatrics
157	MEKONE NKWELE Isabelle	L	Pediatrics
158	TONY NENGOM Jocelyn	L	Pediatrics
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161	GONSU née KAMGA Hortense	P	Bacteriology
162	LUMA Henry	P	Bacteriology/ Virology
163	MBANYA Dora	P	Hematology
164	TAYOU TAGNY Claude	P	Microbiology/Hematology

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171	NDOUMBA NKENGUE Annick épse MINTYA	SL	Hematology
172	VOUNDI VOUNDI Esther	SL	Virology
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182	BILLONG Serges Clotaire	SL	Public Health
183	KEMBE ASSAH Félix	SL	Epidemiology

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186	ABBA-KABIR HAAMIT-M	L	Pharmacist
187	EYEBE EYEBE Serge Bertrand	L	Public Health /Epidemiology
188	MBA MAADJHOU Berjauline Camille	L	Public Health /Nutritional Epidemiology
189	MOSSUS Tatiana née ETOUNOU AKONO	L	Expert in Health Promotion
190	NGUIPDOP DJOMO Patrick	L	Public Health /Epidemiology
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192	ESSAME OYONO	P	Anatomopathology
193	FEWOU Amadou	P	Anatomopathology
194	MENDIMI NKODO Joseph	AP	Anatomopathology
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196	BISSOU MAHOP	SL	Sports Medicine
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204	GUEWO FOKENG Magellan	L	Biochemistry
205	MBONO SAMBA ELOUMBA Esther Astrid	L	Biochemistry
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207	ASSOMO NDEMBA Peggy Brice	AP	Physiology
208	AZABJI KENFACK Marcel	SL	Physiology
209	DZUDIE TAMDJIA Anastase	SL	Physiology
210	EBELLA DALLE Ernest Remy Hervé	L	Human Physiology
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212	NDIKUM Valentine	SL	Pharmacology
213	ONDOUA NGUELE Marc Olivier	L	Pharmacology
DEPARTMENT OF ORAL, MAXILLO-FACIAL SURGERY AND PERIODONTOLOGY			

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219	LOWE NANTCHOUANG Jacqueline Michèle épouse ABISSEGUE	L	Pediatric Dentistry
220	Jules Julien NDJOH	L	Dental Surgery
221	MBEDE NGA MVONDO Rose	L	Dentistry
222	MENGONG épouse MONEBOULOU Hortense	L	Pediatric Dentistry
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223	NTSAMA ESSOMBA Claudine (HD)	P	Pharmacognosy /Pharmaceutical chemistry
224	NGAMENI Bathélémy	P	Phytochemistry/ Organic Chemistry
225	NGOUPAYO Joseph	P	Phytochemistry/Pharmacognosy
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227	BAYAGA Hervé Narcisse	L	Pharmacy
DEPARTMENT OF PHARMACOTOXICOLOGY AND PHARMACOKINETICS			

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228	FOKUNANG Charles	P	Molecular Biology
229	MPONDO MPONDO Emmanuel	P	Pharmacy
230	TEMBE Estella épouse FOKUNANG	AP	Clinical Pharmacology
231	TABI OMGBA	SL	Pharmacy
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232	NNANGA NGA Emmanuel (HD)	P	Galenical Pharmacy
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234	SOPPO LOBE Charlotte Vanessa	SL	Quality Control of Drugs
235	NYANGONO NDONGO Martin	L	Pharmacy

KEY

- **HD** = Head of Department,
- **P** = Professor
- **AP** = Associate Professor
- **SL** = Senior Lecturer
- **L** = Lecturer

THE HIPPOCRATIC OATH GENEVA DECLARATION 2006

At the time of being admitted as a member of the medical profession:

I solemnly pledge to consecrate my life to the service of humanity;

I will give to my teachers the respect and gratitude that is their due;

I will practice my profession with conscience and dignity;

The health of my patient will be my first consideration;

I will respect the secrets that are confided in me, even after the patient has died;

I will maintain by all the means in my power, the honor and the noble traditions of

The medical profession;

My colleagues will be my sisters and brothers;

I will not permit considerations of age, disease or disability, creed, ethnic origin,

*Gender, nationality, political affiliation, race, sexual orientation, social standing or
any*

Other factor to intervene between my duty and my patient;

I will maintain the utmost respect for human life;

i will not use my medical knowledge to violate human rights and civil liberties, even

Under threat;

I make these promises solemnly, freely and upon my honor

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LISTS OF ABBREVIATIONS

- ILO** : International Labor Organization
- PTSD** : Post Traumatic Stress Disorder
- UNESCO** : United Nations Educational, Scientific and Cultural Organization
- WHO** : World Health Organization
- HIV** : Human Immune Deficiency Virus
- WPVH** : Work Place Violence and Harrasment
- ICT** : Information and Communications Technology
- COVID** : Corona Virus Disease
- NGO** : Non-Governmental Organization

ABSTRACT

Title: Teachers Experiences of Work Place Violence and Harassment committed by learners in secondary schools in Yaounde VII

Background: The school is the work place for the teacher. Unfortunately, school violence against teachers is a growing concern globally, affecting not only the safety and well-being of educators but also the overall educational environment. This study investigates the prevalence of various forms of violence experienced by teachers in secondary schools within the Yaounde VII subdivision and examines its impact on their professional well-being and attrition intentions.

Methods: This cross-sectional descriptive study was conducted from March to September 2024, with data collection occurring between June and August 2024. The study population consisted of full-time secondary school teachers with at least 12 months of in-person teaching experience. A sample size of 385 participants was calculated using Andrew Fisher's formula. A self-administered pre-tested questionnaire was used to gather data on experiences of violence, teacher well-being, and thoughts about attrition. Descriptive statistics, chi-square tests, Student's t-tests, and hierarchical multiple linear regression analyses were employed for data analysis, with a significance level set at $p < 0.05$.

Results: A total of 294 teachers participated in the study, with a majority being female (62.9%) and aged between 21-30 years (69.4%). Psychosocial violence was the most commonly reported, with 76.9% of teachers witnessing such incidents. Sexual violence was reported by 33%, while 52% experienced physical violence. Despite these challenges, 67.3% of teachers felt they were effective in their roles,

and 62.5% reported a sense of belonging and safety at their schools. However, 15% considered changing schools, and 13.3% contemplated early retirement due to violence.

Conclusions: The study highlights a significant prevalence of violence against teachers in Yaounde VII, impacting their professional well-being and retention. While many teachers show resilience, a notable minority is at risk of burnout and attrition. Addressing this issue requires comprehensive strategies from the Ministry of Education and other stakeholders to ensure a safer and more supportive school environment.

Recommendations: Interventions should include improved security measures, professional development for teachers on conflict management, and enhanced reporting and support systems. Further research is needed to explore the root causes of student-perpetrated violence and its long-term effects on teacher well-being and professional trajectories in our context.

RESUME

Titre : Expériences des enseignants concernant la violence et le harcèlement au travail commis par les élèves dans les écoles secondaires de Yaoundé VII

Contexte : L'école est le lieu de travail des enseignants. Malheureusement, la violence scolaire à l'encontre des enseignants est un problème croissant à l'échelle mondiale, affectant non seulement leur sécurité et bien-être, mais aussi l'ensemble de l'environnement éducatif. Cette étude examine la prévalence des différentes formes de violence subies par les enseignants dans les écoles secondaires de la subdivision de Yaoundé VII et évalue son impact sur leur bien-être professionnel et leur intention de quitter la profession.

Méthodes : Cette étude descriptive transversale a été menée de mars à septembre 2024, avec une collecte de données effectuée entre juin et août 2024. La population étudiée comprenait des enseignants à plein temps dans les écoles secondaires, ayant au moins 12 mois d'expérience d'enseignement en présentiel. Une taille d'échantillon de 385 participants a été calculée à l'aide de la formule d'Andrew Fisher. Un questionnaire auto-administré pré-testé a été utilisé pour recueillir des données sur les expériences de violence, le bien-être des enseignants et leurs intentions de quitter la profession. Des statistiques descriptives, des tests du chi-deux, des tests t de Student et des analyses de régression linéaire multiple hiérarchique ont été utilisés pour l'analyse des données, avec un seuil de signification fixé à $p < 0,05$.

Résultats : Au total, 294 enseignants ont participé à l'étude, dont une majorité de femmes (62,9 %) et d'âge compris entre 21 et 30 ans (69,4 %). La violence

psychosociale a été la plus fréquemment rapportée, avec 76,9 % des enseignants ayant été témoins de tels incidents. La violence sexuelle a été rapportée par 33 % des enseignants, tandis que 52 % ont subi des violences physiques. Malgré ces défis, 67,3 % des enseignants ont estimé être efficaces dans leurs fonctions et 62,5 % ont ressenti un sentiment d'appartenance et de sécurité dans leurs établissements. Cependant, 15 % ont envisagé de changer d'école et 13,3 % ont pensé à prendre leur retraite anticipée en raison de la violence.

Conclusions : L'étude met en évidence une prévalence significative de la violence à l'encontre des enseignants à Yaoundé VII, impactant leur bien-être professionnel et leur rétention. Bien que de nombreux enseignants fassent preuve de résilience, une minorité notable est à risque de burnout et de départ. Pour remédier à ce problème, il est nécessaire de mettre en place des stratégies globales par le Ministère de l'Éducation et d'autres parties prenantes afin de garantir un environnement scolaire plus sûr et plus favorable.

Recommandations : Les interventions devraient inclure l'amélioration des mesures de sécurité, le développement professionnel des enseignants sur la gestion des conflits et le renforcement des systèmes de signalement et de soutien. Des recherches supplémentaires sont nécessaires pour explorer les causes profondes de la violence perpétrée par les élèves et ses effets à long terme sur le bien-être des enseignants et leur trajectoire professionnelle dans notre contexte.

CHAPTER ONE: INTRODUCTION

1.1: Context and Background

Everyone has the right to work, not only to work but to work in favorable conditions according to article 23 of the Universal Declaration of Human Rights (1). The dignity of work can only be preserved if the work place is safe and healthy.

Work place violence and Harassment however, has been identified as a major work place psychosocial risk factor and is a rising concern (2,3).

What is Work Place Violence and Harassment? This notion has been defined by the International Labour Organisation as ‘a range of unacceptable behaviors and practices, or threats there of whether a single occurrence or repeated, that aim at, result in or a likely to result in physical, psychological, sexual or economic harm, and includes gender-based violence and harassment’(4).

In 2019, the ILO declared in Convention C190, recommendation No 206 against all forms of violence and harassment in the world of work thus recognizing once again the right to safe and decent work for everyone.(4)

Work place violence has many negative consequences on the victim, institution and the society at large. It results in serious consequences to the mental and physical health of the worker including physical harm, psychosomatic diseases like anxiety, insomnia, PTSD, depression, stress, burnout, musculoskeletal symptoms, hypertension (5–8) . Apart from health consequences, Work Place Violence and Harassment negatively impacts the quality of service rendered, worker engagement and thereby, reducing, enterprise sustainability, productivity and reputation(9).

Work place violence and harassment has been observed in different milieus including the school milieu.

In fact, according to UNESCO, school violence is widespread, affects all countries and can be perpetrated by other learners, teachers or others in the school community(9). Traditionally, it seemed more likely hear of violence inflicted on learners by teachers. As a result, there have been many studies to understand the violence inflicted on learners by the teachers and its consequences. (10–12)

Although previously uncommon in our context, there has been a surge in cases of violence and harassment against teachers inflicted by learners in recent times and some of these incidents have made breaking news headlines in the news outlets (13–15).

For the teachers, the school environment is their work place and they have been more recently a growing target for violence inflicted by learners. (13–15). This is a growing challenge globally and sadly it affects the work place of the teacher negatively.

Limited research especially in our milieu have sort to shed more light on this preoccupying situation(16).

We therefore designed this quantitative study to try to understand the prevalence of this problem in Yaounde VII, its effect on teacher's well-being and their perceptions on attrition.

1.2: Justification and interest

The consequences of work place violence experienced by teachers are can be very devastating for the teacher as well as the students. Apart from the consequence on mental and physical health, it may affect the performance at school, work environment, job satisfaction and may result in the loss of skilled workers leaving the profession. Continuous monitoring and intervening to prevent school violence is therefore crucial.

1.3: Research Questions

1. What is the prevalence of work place violence committed by learner on teachers in Yaounde VII?
2. What are the impacts of these experiences on the teacher's work-related wellbeing?
3. What from the teacher's thoughts with regards to attrition?

1.4: Objectives of the study

1.4.1 General objective

- To understand work place violence committed by learners against teachers and its effect on teachers' work related wellbeing in secondary schools in Yaounde VII.

1.4.2 Specific objectives

- Describe the sociodemographic status of teachers in Yaounde VII
- Determine the types and prevalence work place violence committed by learners on teachers.
- Evaluate the teachers work related wellbeing.
- Assess the relation between learner committed violence and the teacher's thoughts on attrition.

CHAPTER 2: REVIEW OF LITTERATURE

In this section, we will revisit existing literature on work place violence and violence in schools with a focus on learner to teacher violence both globally and locally. The focus of this review will be to understand the prevalence, the contributing factors, the consequences and the proposed intervention strategies suggested by many researchers.

2.1: Definition of the concepts

For a better understanding it is imperative to succinctly define the key words and concepts.

2.1.1: Workplace Violence and Harassment

Work place violence and harassment has been defined by Wynne, Clarkin, Cox and Griffiths (17) as “Incidents where staff are abused, threatened or assaulted in circumstances related to their work, involving an explicit or implicit challenge to their safety, well-being or health”. This definition is used in papers **Violence at work** by Chappell and Di Martino 2006 (18).

The concept of work place violence refers therefore to a range of physical, verbal and nonverbal actions intended to create harm either physically or not to a worker. This concept has sometimes been referred to as simply work place violence or work-related violence although implying the same.

The ILO, in her convention No 190 states thus

‘(a) the term “violence and harassment” in the world of work refers to a range of unacceptable behaviors and practices, or threats thereof, whether a single occurrence or repeated, that aim at, result in, or are likely to result in physical, psychological, sexual or economic harm, and includes gender-based violence and harassment;’ (19).

2.1.1.1: Types of work place violence and harassment

The WHO defines violence as “the intentional use of physical force or power, threatened or actual, against oneself, another person, or against a group or community, which either results in or has a high likelihood of resulting in injury, death, psychological harm, maldevelopment, or deprivation (20).

Violence is therefore a complex and heterogenous issue with no single universal categorization.

In terms of origin, the Californian Occupational Safety and health Administration (Cal/OSHA) has defined 3 types and this has become accepted internationally

Type I: The aggressor has no legitimate employment relationship to the worker or the workplace and, usually, the main object of the violence is obtaining cash or valuable property, or demonstrating power. Examples are robbery, mugging and road rage.

Type II: The aggressor is someone who is the recipient of a service provided by the affected workplace or by the worker. Examples are assault or verbal threats by patients, carers or relatives of the patient, learners on teachers. This type of violence is the focus of our study.

Type III: The aggressor is another employee, a supervisor, manager or a relation. Examples are bullying and harassment by the supervisor, current/ former spouse/lover, friend etc

2.1.1.2: Kinds of work place violence

In terms of kinds, work place violence can generally vary from physical to nonphysical, overt to covert, direct to indirect set of behaviors and may sometimes be combined. Moreover, one single event might not be perceived as violence, but repeated actions can accumulate to constitute violence.(21)

The European Agency for Safety and Health at Work distinguishes between Physical, Psychological and and Sexual violence (22). Each of these can be subdivided into specific acts of violence, e.g. assault, abuse, bullying, mobbing, harassment, sexual harassment, racial harassment, threat, etc. All of these terms are common in literature on work-related violence and various definitions exist.

The most common definitions will be described.

In the table below is an overview of the scope of each of these terms and the corresponding type of work-related violence affected (physical, psychological or sexual).

PHYSICAL VIOLENCE	PSYCHOLOGICAL VIOLENCE	SEXUAL VIOLENCE
Assault Physical Abuse Murder	Threat and verbal abuse Psychological abuse Bullying Mobbing Harrassment	Sexual Harassement Unwanted sexual attention Stalking Rape

Table 1. Physical, psychological and sexual violence and their associated concepts.

(The term **abuse** “is used to indicate all behaviours which depart from reasonable conduct and involve the misuse of physical or psychological strength”

The term **bullying/mobbing** “is used to indicate a form of psychological harassment consisting of repetitive persecution through vindictive, cruel, or malicious attempts to humiliate or undermine an individual or groups of employees, including unjustified, constant negative remarks or criticisms, isolating a person from social contacts and gossiping or spreading false information.” It can include cyber bullying. While mobbing is perpetuated by a group of people, bullying is usually done by an individual.

The term **Harassment** “is used to indicate Unwanted conduct – verbal, non-verbal, visual, psychological or physical – based on age, disability, HIV status, domestic circumstances, sex, sexual orientation, race, color, language, religion, political, trade union or other opinion or belief, national or social origin, association with a minority, birth or other status that negatively affects the dignity of men and women at work. It includes sexual harassment.

The term **Sexual Harrasment** “is used to indicate unwanted conduct that is perceived by the victims as placing conditions of a sexual nature on their employment, or that might, on reasonable grounds, be perceived by the victims as an offence, a humiliation or a threat to their well-being

The term **threat** “encompass the menace of death, or the announcement of an intention to harm a person or to damage their property” (18)

2.1.1.2.1: Physical Violence:

The WHO and the ILO define physical violence in a joint questionnaire as “The use of physical force against another person or group, that results in physical, sexual or psychological harm. Includes beating, kicking, slapping, stabbing, shooting, pushing, biting, pinching” (23). It therefore incorporates assaults, physical abuse and murder. This type of violence is more common in some types of

professions like police force, bank tellers, personnel working late at night, teachers and staff working in health care and social services. (24)

2.1.1.2.2: Psychological violence

This type of violence has received increased attention in recent years. It can be defined as the “ intentional use of power, including threat of physical force, against another person or group that can result in harm to physical, mental, spiritual, moral or social development. It includes verbal abuse, bullying/mobbing, harassment and treats” (23). Di Martino et al state that “psychological violence is often perpetrated through repeated behaviour, of a type, which alone may be relatively minor but which cumulatively can become a very serious form of violence” (18). Psychological violence is not always easy to detect as sometimes the behavior is borderline between what constitutes normal behavior and what is not. This type of violence is often associated with emotional abuse and it constitutes unwelcomed, repeated behavior that has serious negative psychological consequences for the victim. This is often the case with verbal abuse, bullying and mobbing. Workers most exposed to this kind of violence are minority workers, migrant workers, worker with handicap, young workers and female workers although this kind of violence can be seen in any worker.

2.1.1.2.3: Sexual Violence

According to the WHO “Sexual violence is any sexual act, attempt to obtain a sexual act, or other act directed against a person’s sexuality using coercion, by any person regardless of their relationship to the victim, in any setting. It includes rape, defined as the physically forced or otherwise coerced penetration of the vulva or anus with a penis, other body part or object.”

The ILO Committee of Experts on the Application of Standards and Recommendations (CEACR), remarked that sexual harassment was a form of discrimination and could be understood as “any physical, verbal or non-verbal conduct of a sexual nature and other conduct based on sex affecting the dignity of women and men, which is unwelcome, unreasonable, and offensive to the recipient; and a person's rejection of, or submission to, such conduct is used explicitly or implicitly as a basis for a decision which affects that person's job”; it could also relate to “conduct that creates an intimidating, hostile or humiliating working environment for the recipient” (23).

Sexual harassment is far from a reciprocal expression of attraction. Piotrkovski established that t “sexual harassment is neither an innocent flirtation nor the mutual expression of attraction between men and women. Rather, sexual harassment is a workplace stressor that poses a threat to a woman’s psychological and physical integrity and security, in a context in which she has little control because of the risk of retaliation and the fear of losing her livelihood” it is important to note that sexual harassment affects men too. (25) A challenge with the concept of sexual violence is the varying cultures across the globe making it difficult to set universally acceptable boundaries to define behavior that is accepted and behavior that is not accepted in normal social interaction between sexes.

2.1.2: The Worker or Employee.

The ILO organization in her convention No 198, 2006 on Employment relationship recommendation, provides non-binding guidance on criteria to be used to determine the existence of an employment relationship. Therefore, the definition of a worker or an employee may vary from country to country.

In Cameroon, the Labour Code states thus; ‘Is considered a "worker" within the meaning of this law, whatever their sex and nationality, any person who has undertaken to place their professional activity for remuneration, under the direction and authority of a natural person or moral, public or private, the latter being considered as an “employer”. When determining the status of worker, neither the legal status of the employer nor that of the employee must be considered.’

Although this law doesn’t apply directly to civil servants, the state acknowledges the need for the protection of the health of their employees. General Status of the public service in Article 31 alinea 2 states that ‘the State is required to ensure the protection of civil servants against accidents and illnesses’

The ILO also declares that the worker or the person in the world of work includes ‘employees as defined by national law and practice, as well as persons working irrespective of their contractual status, persons in training, including interns and apprentices, workers whose employment has been terminated, volunteers, jobseekers and job applicants, and individuals exercising the authority, duties or responsibilities of an employer’ (19).

As such, violence on a worker occurring at the work site or as a result of work shall be considered as work place violence.

2.1.3: The Teacher

According to the Cambridge dictionary a teacher is a person who instructs or trains others especially in a school. (26) Although today, the role of a teacher goes beyond simply instructing or training as teachers show substantial leadership that could greatly influence the learner beyond the instructions.

In their article titled ‘A journey of Teacher education...’ Dori Lal and Jamia Millia defined a teacher as;

‘A **‘teacher’** is a person who delivers an educational program, assesses student participation in an educational program, and/or administers or provides consistent and substantial leadership to an educational program. Teacher is the second parent who thinks good for our future and teacher is the only person who helps us to make decision that is right for us’ (27)

2.1.4: The Learner

The Britannica dictionary describes a learner as ‘a person who is trying to gain knowledge or skill in something by studying, practicing, or being taught’. (28)

In the context of this study, the learner refers to the students enrolled in schools for the purpose of gaining knowledge and are being taught by the teacher. The 1996 constitution of Cameroon guarantees the right of every child to education.

2.1.5: Secondary school

The Cambridge dictionary defines secondary school as a school attended by children aged between 11 and 18 approximately after elementary school.(26)

Law no 98/004 of 14 April 1998 on the orientation of education in Cameroon in article 16, describes secondary education as the 7 year period of education after primary school. In Cameroon, It consist of 2 sub-systems; the Anglophone and Francophone sub systems.

2.1.6: School violence

UNESCO defines school violence as “all forms of violence that takes place inside or outside of the classroom, around schools, on the way to or from school, as well as in online and other digital environments.”

The Center for the Prevention of School Violence developed a research-based definition of “school violence” in 1997. The definition suggests that “school violence is any behavior that violates a school’s educational mission or climate of respect or jeopardizes the intent of the school to be free of aggression against persons or property, drugs, weapons, disruptions, and disorder” (29)

2.2 WORK PLACE VIOLENCE AND HARASSMENT; A GLOBAL OVERVIEW

WPVH transcends the boundaries of individual countries, industry sectors and occupational groups. No country, work setting or occupation can claim to be entirely free of any form of workplace violence and harassment (24).

Global studies are rare but a first global survey was done by the ILO and the Lloyds Register foundation in 2021 and provided a lot of insight into the magnitude of this problem.

Work place violence and harassment is a global problem affecting more than one in five people globally. (30)

Across the world, 22.8 percent or 743 Million employees had experienced violence and harassment at work whether physical , psychological or sexual over their working life. 79% of these victims report the last occurrence was in the last 5 years prior to completing the survey.

The prevalence of WPVH varies with the highest rates in the Americas at 34.3% followed by Africa at 25.7%.

The phenomenon can be quite complex and difficult to explore as the victims usually do not report. Infact, only 50% of victims worldwide report their experiences

of work place violence and harassment to someone else, and often only after they had been victim of more than one form of WPVH. The main reasons for non-disclosure is the sensation of a “waste of time” and the “fear for their reputation”.

While it was noticed that in high income countries, more women were victim of some form of WPVH, in middle- and low-income countries, it was rather noticed that the majority of victims of WPVH were men.

Globally however, younger people were more likely to experience WPVH compared to older people.

According to this report, globally, nearly one in ten persons had experienced physical violence and harassment at the work in the working life. Psychological violence such as insults, threats, bullying intimidation occurred more frequently affecting nearly one in five people in employment during their working life with more than 50% reporting multiple experiences. One in 15 people in employment globally had experienced sexual violence and harassment at work such as unwanted touching, sexual requests, pictures, comments emails etc in their working life. Women were more likely than men to have experienced recurrent sexual violence and harassment at work.

Conscious of this surging problem, the ILO in her convention No 190 and recommendation No 206 proposed the first international labour standards to provide a common frame work to prevent, remedy and eliminate violence and harassment in the world of work including gender-based violence and harassment. For the first time in international law, the right to decent work is a human right. In section IV. Protection and Prevention Article 9 (b) it states that Each member shall adopt laws and regulations requiring employers to..... ‘take into account violence and

harassment and associated psychosocial risks in the management of occupational safety and health;’

The employer be it in the private or public sector needs to take measures to protect her employees from WPVH without discrimination. (30)

2.3: WORK PLACE VIOLENCE AND HARASSMENT IN AFRICA

As already mentioned, WPVH in Africa accounts for about 25.7% of cases of WPVH worldwide. Across Africa, the prevalence of WPVH varies across different countries. We found some studies regarding the prevalence of work place violence in different occupations. Most of the studies found had been done in the domain of health care.

Stanley Njaka et al (31) in their systematic review of WPVH against health care workers in Africa found that the prevalence varied ranging from 9% to 100% with the highest in South Africa (54%-100%) and Egypt (59.7%-86.1%). The common types were verbal, physical, sexual harassment and psychological violence. Tshifularo Olga Mahani et al (32) in their study to evaluate work place violence against nurses in South Africa found that 85% of their respondent had experienced WPVH in the last 12 months with a range of 95% for threats to 60% for bullying and most especially amongst psychiatric nurses.

Louise Knight et al (33) who sort to describe the prevalence of and the risk factors for work place violence among Ugandan adolescents between 2014-2019 found that overall 40% of paid adolescent workers experienced past-year work place violence with the Odds doubled amongst female domestic workers (Vs retail/trade workers). The experiences were mostly severe physical violence, bullying, starvation.

Concerning gender based violence, Parinita Bhattacharjee et al (34) in their study on the prevalence and patterns of gender-based violence across adolescent girls and young women in Mombasa, Kenya, found that the prevalence of lifetime and recent experience of sexual violence were 20.5% and 9.8% respectively. Olaoluwa Samson Agbaje et al (35) found that work place gender based violence amongst university women in Enugu, Nigeria was quite high, affecting 40.5% of participants in the study.

Bewunetu Zewude et al (36) found that work place violence against waitress in Ethiopia is especially high within certain jobs like catering, agriculture, hotels, restaurants, transport and manufacturing sectors. They also noted that the level of exposure to violence varies across different circumstances, including working in large and small towns, the situation of the owner/ supervisors, public insights, ability to speak local language amongst others.

In a mixed study in Gambia, Ebrima J Sisawo et al (37) found that 62.1% of nurses had been exposed to violence in the last year. Verbal abuse was the most common abuse (59.8%).

Mehdi Ben Khelil et al (38) in a retrospective study found that work place homicides in northern Tunisia between 2003-2017 was a consequence work place violence affecting men with a sex ratio of 49:1. The occupations most at risk were security guards and taxi drivers. The perpetrator was mostly unknown and the motive being robbery.

2.4 WORK PLACE VIOLENCE AND HARASSMENT IN CAMEROON

Work place violence and harassment is a reality in Cameroon. Some studies have been done to understand this phenomenon.

In a study in 2018, Jules Owona et al found that (39) found that 77.87% of health personnel in Yaounde had been victims of some form of WPVH. This violence was mostly type II verbal violence perpetrated by the persons accompanying the patients. In another study Jules Owona et al in 2020 (40) found that 68.84% of security agents in Douala had been victims of work place violence and harassment. This violence affected mostly men and the main type of violence experienced was verbal violence.

Michele R Decker et al found that Gender based violence against female sex workers in Cameroon was quite high and undermines HIV prevention and access to health care and justice. 60% of participants had experienced physical or sexual violence. Anna Abelson et al (41) found that the lifetime sexual violence was prevalent with 33.0% among female sex workers in Cameroon which is significantly higher than in the general population.

There is a need to do more research in this area nationally.

2.5: CONSEQUENCES OF WORK PLACE VIOLENCE

Violence and harassment at work can have serious consequences not just on its immediate targets. Other potential “victims” include colleagues, family members, friends, patients and clients and the society at large.

Health wise, violence at work may ultimately affect a person’s health, well-being and dignity.

As a result of WPVH, many individuals may suffer from a range of serious mental and physical injuries.

Several studies have described conditions like guilt, anxiety, depression, distrust, disbelief, stress, deterioration of quality of life and powerlessness ((5,42–

45) They may suffer post traumatic stress disorder and various nervous symptoms (42,46)). Other responses include reactions such as shock, despair, anger, helplessness, sleep problems (6,46,47), chronic fatigue, and increased suicide risk (48)

A systematic review of the literature suggested that there might be a clear association between work place bullying and suicidal ideation (49). WPVH is the leading cause of work place fatalities. (48)

In addition, victims may ‘self-medicate’ with drugs and alcohol (50) and become socially isolated when their relationships with work colleagues, friends and families deteriorate as a consequence of violence and harassment (51)

From a physical perspective, targets commonly suffer from decreased physical strength and musculoskeletal complaints(48) heightened risk of cardiovascular disease (52,53) such as increased cortisol levels and an elevated heart rate(54) Furthermore, the most severe forms of sexual violence – namely, forced sexual intercourse or rape – can result in serious physical injuries, unwanted pregnancies and the transmission of sexually transmitted diseases, including the HIV virus (55)

In addition, if a worker complains about violence and harassment, the complaint may trigger retaliation and reduce professional, psychological, and physical well-being; however, failing to complain and enduring the violence without resisting also takes its toll in terms of health (56)

The presence of violence and harassment in the workplace can have a detrimental effect on individuals’ mental health even if they are not personally victimized, including witnesses and other co-workers (57,58). Other secondary

victims include family and friends, who may be harmed vicariously through losing partners, parents and other family members.

Workplace violence and harassment brings a range of potential adverse impacts in its wake. These include increased worker absenteeism (on account, inter alia, of fear, illness and injury) and higher staff turnover (59). Workers who are exposed to violence and harassment are also more likely to make errors at work and provide compromised levels of services.(44) In the health care sector in particular, this may have potentially catastrophic consequences (60)and result in litigation for professional negligence.

All these factors are linked to consequent increases in recruitment, onboarding and training costs - as well as reduced morale, performance and productivity. (54) Recent studies have recognized that exposure to bullying increases the risk of sick leave by more than 60 per cent (61).

The organizational fallout caused by workplace violence and harassment may lead to reduced business profitability, poor reputation, difficulty getting and keeping skilled workers, increased insurance premiums (including in relation to workers' compensation), an increased use of and cost to the health system, and a range of other adverse impacts on the economy (62) .

Furthermore, workplace violence and harassment may have indirect adverse impacts on organizations through customer and client behaviour and poor outcomes. For example, clients may express dissatisfaction to external bodies, change their purchasing behaviours, lodge complaints and/or or become litigious. Economic consequences associated with change in client/customer behaviours will grow over time if the incidence and severity of occupational violence and harassment goes unchecked or multiplies (60,63).

Violence and harassment at the workplace may also have consequences for society as a whole, in terms of costs related to social and health services and welfare. These costs include those related to medical consultations, treatment and/or rehabilitation, as well as expenditure for social welfare/benefits due to premature retirement - and the more intangible costs related to loss of productive workers at a premature stage (64).

One can observe that the consequences of unchecked work place violence and harassment can be devastating for the victim, the institution and the society and therefore should be carefully considered and addressed by the authorities.

2.6: ADDRESSING WORK PLACE VIOLENCE

2.6.1: The regulatory frame work

2.6.1.1: International Labor Standards

As mentioned, the ILO adopted the Violence and Harassment Convention, 2019 (No. 190), and its accompanying Recommendation (No. 206). The new standards recognize the right of everyone to a world of work free from violence and harassment – and call for it to be prohibited, prevented and addressed in relevant laws and policies, as well as through collective bargaining. By adopting these instruments, the global community has made it clear that violence and harassment in the world of work will not be tolerated and must end.

A number of other OSH instruments set out to protect workers safety and health. Although they do not mention violence and harassment specifically, they are recognized health risk.

These include

The Occupational Safety and Health Convention, 1981 (No. 155), its accompanying Recommendation (No. 164) and Protocol of 2002 (No. 155)

The Occupational Health Services Convention, 1985 (No. 161) and its accompanying Recommendation (No. 171);

The Promotional Framework for Occupational Safety and Health Convention, 2006 (No. 187) and its accompanying Recommendation (No. 197).

The ILO list of Occupational diseases now covers mental and behavioral disorders, including PTSD and other mental disorders not mentioned but show a direct link with work activities.

2.6.1.2 National Occupational health and safety laws and regulations

Most countries have some form of regulation or legislation stipulating that employers have the obligation to ensure and protect the health and safety of their workers at the workplace. This obligation implicitly includes both physical and psychological health although it may not explicitly mention violence and harrassment.

In Cameroon, decree No 039/MTPS/IMT of 26 November 1984 fixing measure of hygiene and safety at the work place stipulate in Chapter 1, Article 2- 1 that the employer is directly responsible for the application of all the preventive, hygiene and safety measures destined to assure the protection of the health of the workers he uses (65).

The 1994 General Civil Status Act in article 31 -2 states that the state is responsible for assuring the protection of the civil servant from all diseases and accidents of occupational origin(66).

The organizational chart of the Ministry of Secondary Education in Cameroon in Article 70 places Hygiene and security at work under the authority of the Service head of the Social and Welfare Service (67)

2.6.2: Interventions to prevent work place violence.

The different work places have different means by which they implement preventive measures within the existing legal frame work.

The ILO recommends a participatory approach where all parties are considered worthwhile to work together in reducing work place related stress and violence. Create a trust environment and encourage employees to share their feelings openly and their ideas for changes in the work environment. Involve trade unions to create awareness and activate joint employee-management operational bodies and programs to combat WPVH

It is encouraged to use a step wise approach

2.6.2.1: Recognize Stress

Early recognition of stress at the work place can help permit early interventions. Identification of signs of stress in an individual e.g somatic signs like dry throat, muscle tension, head aches, irritability impulsive behavior excessive worrying etc or identifying risk factors in perpetrators like substance abuse, mental illness, access to weapons, or victims like being young, being a woman etc can help act promptly. While the above features deserve consideration, they are not pathognomonic and should not lead to discrimination.

2.6.2.2: Assess the level of stress

This is a very important step and is usually carried out through a stress audit. A check list of stressors is identified and classified and then a survey is done at the work place. Work characteristics like organizational structure, participation, career development and job status, role, job content, work load and pace, work time, interpersonal relationships at work, preparation and training can be evaluated. Certain work situations may also be of interest like working alone, working in contact with the public, working with valuables and cash handling, working with people in distress, working in an environment increasingly open to violence (violence in school is part of this trend) and working in conditions of special vulnerability.

2.6.2.3: Plan anti stress interventions

Wide ranging interventions may be considered at different levels based on the approach preventive, early detection and curative.

Pre-conditions for effective interventions include:

- Developing a “quality” workplace culture where dialogue and communication are extensively exercised and avoiding authoritarian working environment.
- Issuing a clear policy statement of intent from the top management to recognize the importance of fight against stress and violence at work. It should include a declaration of real commitment to make the issue of WPVH a real priority, a caution stating no tolerance for violent behavior, an engagement in support of any action targeted to creating a stress free environment and a directive stating that supervisors and managers have the duty to implement the policy and to demonstrate leadership by example.

- Raising awareness on the deleterious effects of work place stress and violence and the advantages of taking immediate action to eliminate it.

The different kinds of interventions include;

- Environmental interventions like improving the physical environment and eliminating physical factors like noise, bad odours, poor illumination, extreme temperature, extreme humidity, poor ventilation, dust, vibrations and also by controlling factors like crowding, comforts of seats, improving work station design, installing cameras, systems to alert employees that urgent help is needed etc
- Technological interventions like introducing the use of ICT in a phased way with clear benefits, work arrangements that are human tailored rather than technology driven
- Organizational intervention is equally very important. Interventions like changing work practices e.g rapid efficient services, rostering more staff during peak periods, staff rotation, keeping waiting times to minimum, reducing face to face contact with public when possible, improving cash handling procedures with introduction of Automatic tellers.
- Improving job content, making job more understood by the worker and less monotonous etc and rearranging work time and avoid the massive recourse to over time, create autonomous or semi-autonomous teams managing their own time, minimize night shifts
- Intervention on the individual. Use appropriate selection tests to chose the best persons for the job who will adapt easily to the job stress. Regular and updated training and education is essential to violence prevention. Education on the prevention of work place violence and harassment should be emphasized especially to particularly exposed workers.

- Fitness, proper eating, sleeping habits, relaxation techniques, leisure activities and socialization amongst staff help reduce stress and work place violence.
- Counselling and psychosocial support should be made available. This kind of assistance can be provided by colleagues or by professionals depending on the severity of the case.

2.6.2.4: Monitoring and Evaluation:

It is important to record and report all incidents related to stress and violence including minor and potential incidents where no actual harm has resulted. All employees should be free to report without fear of reprisal or criticism. They should know how and where to report.

Evaluate interventions regularly by providing means for feedback from workers. Review the management plan regularly and hold meetings with workers to evaluate the measures put in place a **Plan- Do- Check- Act** cycle (68)

Several studies have cited aspects of this ILO guide.(69–72).

2.7: TEACHER DIRECTED WORK PLACE VIOLENCE

2.7.1: PREVALENCE AND EXPERIENCES OF WORK PLACE VIOLENCE AGAINST TEACHERS GLOBALLY.

Teacher-directed violence, according to Nielsen and Einarsen (2018), is a worldwide phenomenon with similar features and outcomes present around the world. According to Moon, Morash, Jang and Jeong, (2015), Canada and the United States reported 80% of teachers were victims of verbal, psychological, and physical violence(73). Similarly, 4% of a nationally representative sample of Israeli 7th-11th grade students reported they had threatened to hurt a teacher (74). The Taiwanese situation is not different: a nationally representative sample of 14,022 Taiwanese

youths reported that nearly one-third of students were involved in verbally and/or physically aggressive behavior against teachers (75).

Violence against teachers in their work place can be of varied origins. Sometimes the violence comes from parents, administrators, fellow colleagues and the students. (76,77)

In their metaanalysis Longobardi C et al (78) noted that a lot of research has not been done on this topic. They found 24 articles that met the criteria for the meta-analysis. Their research found that the prevalence of all reported violence on teachers in the last 2 years ranged from 20-75% with a pooled prevalence of 53%. The prevalence of more intrusive types of aggression was however lower than verbal aggression. Wilson CM et al (79) in their study found that 80% of teachers had experienced school related violence at one point in their career. Serious violence eg Actual, attempted, threatened physical violence was less common but still common enough to be of concern (27.6%). They also found in general that women reported higher levels of physical symptoms compared to men. (80,81)

In a qualitative study titled Teachers' Lived Experiences of Workplace Violence and Harassment Committed by Learners from Selected High Schools in Limpopo Province, South Africa, Madie Collen Mangena et al (82) teachers related their experiences of being targets of learner to teacher work place violence which presented as physical violence, nonverbal and verbal violence and harassment. They described really challenging real life experiences that make the workplace very uncondusive for working.

With the advent of the novel Corona Virus, it was noted that violence and threats against teachers had increased with an increase intension to quit the profession or transfer to other schools. (83)

A survey carried out in collaboration with the American Psychological Association Task Force On Violence against Educators conducted in America and found that 43.75 of teachers reported experiencing at least one verbal threat, physical assault and or property damage with verbal threats being the most prevalent form of victimization during the COVID pandemic. In person instruction significantly predicted teacher violence across aggressors. (84)

Violence against teachers is therefore a global phenomenon that is understudied. More studies need to be done to understand the determinants and possible positive interventions.

2.7.2: Prevalence and experiences of violence against teachers in Cameroon.

In Cameroon, we found a few studies that look at violence against teachers. On the 20th-23rd of December 2022 the Ministry of Secondary education organized a symposium on violence in the school milieu in the wake of rising violence in schools in Cameroon. In their report, the ministry declared that statistically, boys (64%), girls (3%), school officials (1%) and people around the school environment (34%) are involved in school violence in Cameroon. She further indicated that 11 cases of aggravated violence were reported in secondary schools from 22 November 2018 to 13 April 2022, the most regretful one being the stabbing to death of a young Mathematics teacher by one of his students at Government High School Nkolbisson, on 14 January 2020. (15)

Benbenishty et al (16) found in their study in Buea and Tiko that students had perpetrated different forms of violence against teachers. The most common types of perpetration against teachers were damaging their personal property (14.9%) and making sexual comments (13.9%). Threatening physical violence

(10.8%) and kicking or punching a teacher (11%) had the lowest (although clearly not negligible) prevalence.

A study in the northwest examined violence in secondary schools but it focused on students and does not examine teacher directed violence (85)

Takang Jaspa David (86) in his paper noted that although violence had been existing in secondary schools in Cameroon, recent years have seen aggravation with extremes as loss of lives have been recorded. Similar finding were observed by Roland in Buea (87)

2.7.3: Risk factors for violence in the school environment

According to most literature, there is no single cause of violence in school but rather a number of contributing factors that sustain the culture of violence in school.

Notably violence in the society in general can easily spill into the school milieu.(88) A prior history of violence is therefore a risk factor for violence in school.

Family situation and parenting style have always been considered as the root of influencing childrens behavior. Research shows that ill parenting is positively correlated with students' violent behaviors at school. (89) Similar studies showed that parental violence was closely correlated with children's aggressiveness and impulsiveness. (90)

Drug, alcohol and tobacco use have been identified not only as cause of school violence but also a consequence of school violence. Under the influence of illicit substances, learners become more violent and aggressive. (91)

Association with delinquent peers has been clearly identified as a risk factor for youth violence. (92) Sometimes this association with delinquent peers tends to make the learners normalize violent behavior. (93)

Community poverty was positively correlated with experiences of violence. Sherry et al (94) found that students in high poverty schools experienced significantly different forms of violence. Similar findings were observed by Elda de Oliveira (95)

In Cameroon, Takang David noted in his study that mental health conditions of the learners, poor academic performance by students, lack of professional behavior by some teachers, aggressive nature of some discipline masters, lack of emphasis on subjects that promote civility like citizenship education, moral studies amongst others contribute to school violence.(86)

These causes are similar to causes cited in several articles online. (96,97)

2.7.3: CONSEQUENCE OF VIOLENCE ON THE TEACHER'S WELLBEING AND PROFESSIONAL PERFORMANCE.

Violence on teachers can be considered at work place violence and has negative consequences on the worker and their professional performance. The consequences include psychological, emotional, biological, professional and social harm . (98)

Several studies have found that stress and burnout was significantly associated with violence at school affecting up to 60% of teachers. (98–101)

Agyapong et al (102) in their scoping review set to determine the extent in current literature on the prevalence and correlates of stress, burnout, anxiety and depression amongst teachers found that the prevalence of burn out ranged from

25.12% to 74%, stress ranged from 8.3% to 87.1%, anxiety ranged from 38% to 41.2% and depression ranged from 4% to 77%. As well as the physical dangers posed by assault, theft, and vandalism, there are psychological and social side effects for teachers that cause anxiety and fear which need to be addressed.

Work violence affects work performance. Albanita et al (103) in Brazil found that teachers who had been victims of some form of violence reported a low physical and emotional work ability (56% and 40.6% of respondents respectively). In their study, they found that the physical, emotional, and future work ability of teachers was low and associated with school violence, indicating the need to promote a safer work environment inside the school and in society as a whole. In Cameroon, Eku Maru Lydian and collaborators established that school safety had an effect on teachers effectiveness in primary schools in Manyu division (104).

Work place violence affects teacher's performance and can make the school dysfunctional if not addressed properly (73) Furthermore, it is confirmed that teacher-directed violence contributes negatively to excellent teaching and increases fear, physical and psychological consequences to the victims, and low learner performance (79)

Teacher directed violence is associated with high teacher turn over and the decision to quit all together. This situation has serious consequences on the quality of learning as qualified skills are difficult to retain.(79,105)

Fisher et al in their study found that 56% of teachers believed that violence or the threat of violence had a direct impact on the quality of education they are able to provide.(106)

One can conclude that the consequences on the teachers wellbeing and professional performance are similar to the consequences of work place violence on

any professional in their job. This further emphasizes the need to ensure the work place is free from violence and harassment.

2.7.4: Addressing school violence

Many interventions have been proposed to address school violence. These interventions follow a similar pattern as proposed by the ILO to address work place violence in general.

UNESCO in her proposal outlined in the School based Violence prevention practical handbook, she outlined a multifaceted approach in the following practical steps ;

- Getting started: Develop leadership, school policies and coordination methods
- Collect data on violence and monitor changes over time
- Prevent violence through curriculum-based activities
- Work with teachers on values and beliefs and train them in positive discipline and classroom management
- Respond to violence when it happens
- Review and adapt school buildings and grounds
- Involve parents in violence prevention activities
- Involve the community in violence prevention activities
- Evaluate violence prevention activities and use the evidence to strengthen your approaches

(107)

Some countries have developed a national policy to address school violence.

A good example is The National School Safety Framework developed by the Ministry of Education in South Africa to address violence in schools.

It is based on 4 pillars which are

- Willingness to prevent and manage safety-related problems: Schools should have updated codes of conduct, safety policies, and procedures for addressing violence and harassment when they arise.
- An awareness of the safety climate of the school: Every school should be aware of its level of safety as well as its resources for making the school safe. There should be regular monitoring, evaluation, and control activities to ensure that violence and harassment are prevented and managed properly if detected.
- Readiness to take action: A school should be ready to respond to early warning signs of workplace violence and harassment. To be able to detect warning signs early, the school should make safety part of its cultural norm. Policies and procedures to manage violence and harassment should be available so that they are implemented in response to early warning signs.
- Building a caring school: A caring school is one that promotes and protects the health and psychophysical wellbeing of teachers and learners so that the two listen to and protect each other. Building a caring school calls for the collective effort of all stakeholders such as social workers, and NGOs.

(108)

In Cameroon, Takang Jaspa in his paper reported suggestions from school administrators on their suggestion to eradicating school violence. He summarized as follows

- Discipline masters must be well trained especially in psychology to handle students varied complaints.
- Having PTA meeting specifically on parental upbringing of children. In this regard principals said during this meeting, guidance counselors and some resource persons will be invited to present papers.

- Seminars/workshops be organized to train teachers on professionalism so as to have knowledge on how to handle students professionally.
- Security agents be recruited and placed in all corners of the school. Their role being to check all students' bags, their pockets who may carry many unwanted items such as knives, drugs, and other items which may cause havoc in school.
- Some principals talk of vigilante committee others talk of crisis management committee to be in place at the beginning of each school year to preempt any unwanted situation or to act immediately when a crisis hit.
- Reintroduction of corporal punishment. This point was echoed by many principals even though some were silent on it.
- Increasing the coefficient of some subjects that could instill core values and discipline in students.

As at now only compulsory subjects have high coefficients. The subjects include citizenship education, philosophy, and religious studies/moral instruction.

- Some principals said the educational system where marks and certificate dominate should be restructured and focuses on a system were acquisition of skills to avoid the issue of failure which could be disappointing to some students.

(86)

At the end of her seminar, the Ministry of Secondary Education in Cameroon came up with 12 points to be implemented in the micro society (i.e. the school environment) and 9 points to be implemented on the society at large. (15) highlighting the fact that violence in school could have significant external contributing factors.

In Uganda 18 months after the implementation of the intervention call Good School Toolkit, evaluation revealed that the risk of physical violence by teachers and school staff against students had reduced by 42% and there was an increase in the

teacher's satisfaction in their role at school with increasing sense of safety at school. (109).

In general, the points could be subclassified as actions under the different recommendations by UNESCO and ILO.

Several studies have shown that targeted interventions at national and school specific level appear to be effective in preventing school violence (110) although some authors have criticized that resources have been used on ineffective interventions. (111)

CHAPTER 3: RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

3.1. Research design and Methods

3.1.1: Study type:

- Cross-Sectional Descriptive study.

3.1.2: Study setting:

- This study was carried out in Yaounde VII sub division.

3.1.3: Study Duration

- This study was carried out between March 2024 till September 2024
- Data collection was between June 2024 till August 2024

3.1.4: Study Population:

- Teachers teaching in secondary schools in Yaounde VII

3.1.5: Inclusion Criteria:

Be a full-time teacher of the Secondary school, accumulating at least 12 months of in person teaching experience, willing to freely participate in the study

3.1.6: Non-Inclusion Criteria:

Refuse to participate in the study

3.1.7: Exclusion Criteria:

Teachers who have served less than 12 months, teachers who teach online only.

3.2. Data Collection tools:

- Self-Administered Pre-tested Questionnaire with multiple choice questions. (appendix 2)
 - Questions regarding the type of violence were asked with respect to the different forms of violence described in literature.
 - Questions regarding teacher wellbeing were adapted from the TSWQ (Teacher Subjective Wellbeing Questionnaire) This scale is self-report, evidence based rating scale designed to assess the subjective wellbeing of teachers within the school environment. It is comprised of 2 sub scales – Teaching efficacy and school correctness
- The study participants were also given an informed consent form (appendix 1)

3.3. Sampling size and procedure

Sample size calculation for participants will be estimated using the Andrew Fishers Formula (112).

$$N = \frac{Z^2 SD(1-SD)}{CI^2}$$

Where;

N = Sample size

Z = 1.96 = Z- Score of which depends on the confidence level. Here we will

Consider the level of significance (α) to be 0.05 and confidence level to be 95%

Corresponding to a Z score of 1.96

CI = Confidence Interval or precision = (+-)5% or 0.05

SD = Standard Deviation of 0.5

Substituting into the formula, calculated sample size (N) will be 385

3.4. Method of analysis

The statistical application SPSS Version 17 was used for analysis.

Tables and graphs were made using Microsoft Excel and Microsoft Word 2013.

Descriptive analysis was conducted to analyze simple descriptive information (i.e., gender, years of service, etc.) of the sample.

Hierarchical multiple linear regression analyses was employed to examine the relationship between the personal characteristics of the teachers in the sample, their experience with school violence, their wellbeing and their thoughts about attrition.

Chi tests, Students test, Fisher tests were used to analyze associations between variables. $P < 0.05$ was considered statistically significant.

3.5. Ethical considerations

Ethical clearance was obtained from the Institutional Committee of Ethics and Research of the Faculty of Medicine and Biomedical Sciences (Appendix?)

Authorization will also be obtained from the Council and the Principal of each school.

The teacher's consent was obtained.

Anonymity and confidentiality of the teachers and the schools was respected.

3.6. Definition of operational terms

Psychosocial violence was defined as all behaviors which depart from reasonable conduct and involve misuse of physical and psychological strength by the student

Sexual violence was defined as unwanted conducts by the students that is perceived as actions of a sexual nature and perceived as offensive

Physical Violence was defined as all behaviors which encompass the menace of death, or the announcement of an intention to harm a person or to damage their property by the student?

Teacher attrition was defined as teachers leaving the profession or those moving between schools.

CHAPTER 4: RESULTS

In total, 294 teachers responded to our questionnaire.

4.1. Sociodemographic profile:

Gender: Amongst the respondents, 185 (62.9%) were female and 109 (37.1%) were male giving a sex ratio of 1.69 with a female majority.

Figure 1: Gender distribution amongst respondents

Age Distribution: 69.4% of respondents were aged between 21-30, followed by 25.2% between 31-40 and smaller percentages in the higher age groups

Official Language: Most participants spoke French (71.1%), while the rest spoke English.

Responsibilities: The most common role was class teacher 66%, followed by class master (11.6%) and others such as discipline master and counsellor.

Working Experience: 73.1% had 5 years of working experience and only 1.7% had more than 10 years of working experience. Amongst our respondents, 73.5% had been working in the same school since 5 years.

A significant majority were Christians (94.9%), while Muslims represented 3.7% of the sample.

Characteristic	Number of Respondents	Percentage	Number of Female respondents	Percentage Female	Number of Male respondents	Percentage Male
Gender of respondents	294	100%	185	62.9%	109	37.1%
Age between 21-30	204	69.4%	132	64.7%	72	35.3%
French as First language	209	71.1%	137	65.6%	72	34.4%
Responsibility: Class teacher	194	66%	128	66.0%	66	34.0%
Responsibility: Class Master	34	11.6%	18	52.9%	16	47.1%
Christian Faith	279	94.9%	175	62.7%	104	37.3
Experience between 1-5 years	215	73.1%	150	67%	74	33.0%

Table 2: Summary of the demographic characteristics according to gender.

4.2. Types of Violence

4.2.1. Psychosocial violence

In the last year a large percentage of teachers ie 76.9% (226) of teachers reported had witnessed some form of psychosocial violence perpetuated on a teacher by a student.

Concerning the different types of psychosocial violence, verbal threats were frequent. At least 66.9% had either sometimes or fairly often witnessed verbal threats

whereas only 25.5% never witnessed any. Less common were bullying, mobbing and internet/social media victimization with 83.7%, 82.7% and 86.2% reported never experiencing such type of violence.

Figure 2: Types of Psychosocial Violence Experienced by teachers in the last year in Yaounde VII

4.2.2. Sexual Violence

Concerning sexual violence perpetrated by learners on teachers, 33% of teachers reported having been victims of some form of actions of sexual nature perceived as offensive (99 respondents).

Obscene remarks and gestures were the most common forms of sexual harassment, with 14.3 and 8.2% reporting these experiences sometimes. Stalking

and unwanted sexual remarks were reported, though less frequently, with the majority of teachers never experiencing these behaviors.

Obscene gestures were at least sometimes or fairly often experienced by 11.7% of the respondents in the last year

Stalking was experienced sometimes or fairly often by 9.2% of the respondents

Unwanted sexual remarks had been experienced sometimes or fairly often by 8.5% of the respondents

No respondent had experienced or witnessed rape in the last year

Figure 3: Types of Sexual Violence Experienced by teachers in the last year in Yaounde VII

4.2.3. Physical Violence

Concerning physical violence, 52.0% of respondents reported to have experienced or witnessed some form of physical violence in the last year.

Some teachers experienced objects being thrown (10.5% of respondents had at least some times or fairly often experienced objects being thrown at them in the last year)

More severe forms such as physical attack (9.5%), weapons being pulled (10.9%) theft of property (10.8%) or damage to personal property (10.1%) were witnessed by teachers.

Figure 4: Types of Physical Violence Experienced by teachers in the last year in Yaounde VII

4.3. Wellbeing at school.

The teachers subjective wellbeing questionnaire was used to evaluate the wellbeing of the teachers.

It was comprised of 2 sections ie teaching efficacy, and school correctedness. 4 questions were used to evaluate each of these notions

4.3.1. Teaching efficacy;

67.3% of teachers often felt that they were successful teachers despite the school violence in the last year, 61% often felt that they were good at helping students learn new things, 65.6 % often felt that they had accomplished a lot in the last year. Over all 65.32% respondents therefore had a score of 6/8, meaning they have often felt as efficient teachers in the last year. 20.8% of respondents had a score of 8/8 meaning they felt they had been efficient teachers almost always during the course of the last year. Only a minority (1.27%) had a score of 2/8 indicating they have never been efficient teachers in the last year.

4.3.2. School correctedness:

62.2% of teacher felt like they belonged at school, 61.2% often felt safe at school, 59.9% of teachers often felt like the people at school cared about them, 67% often felt they were treated with respect

In summary, regarding school correctedness, 62.5% of respondents had a score of 6/8 ie reported they often felt comfortable and a sense of belonging to the school in the last year while 14.1% reported having that feeling almost always. Only 1% of respondents reported never feeling comfortable and correct at school.

Figure 5: Teachers Subjective Wellbeing- Teaching Effectiveness

Figure 6: Teachers Subjective Wellbeing- School Correctedness

4.4. Attrition

Almost 85.1% had never thought of changing school in the last year because of violence. However a minority of teachers either sometimes (8.8%) or often (5.1%) considered changing.

Most teachers (88.1%) also had never thought of changing profession due to violence. However at least 11.5% either sometimes or often times (5.4%) thought of changing profession in the last year.

13.3% of teachers sometimes or often times thought of retiring early considering the level of violence at school.

CHAPTER 5: DISCUSSIONS

5.1. Sociodemographic profile

The demographic data of the teachers responding to this study reflects a young and predominantly female workforce, with a significant majority having less than five years of experience. This profile may contribute to the high levels of vulnerability and susceptibility to workplace violence reported as was reported by Holt and collaborators(81). The high proportion of French-speaking teachers (71.1%) also reflects the linguistic distribution of the region, which may have implications for communication and support mechanisms in a bilingual country like Cameroon.

5.2. Types of Violence

5.2.1.Psychosocial Violence:

The study highlights a concerning prevalence of psychosocial violence, with 76.9% of teachers reporting witnessing such behavior. Verbal threats were the most frequent form of psychosocial violence, experienced by nearly 67% of teachers. These results are similar to the 25-75% range of psychosocial violence and the 67% of verbal threats that Longobardi C et al (78) noted in their metaanalysis. It is also similar to the 68.8% of mostly verbal threats observed amongst security agents in Douala by Jules Owona et al in 2020 (40). The high levels of verbal abuse questions the efficacy of disciplinary frameworks and administrative support, the reason why such behaviors to persist. The low occurrence of bullying, mobbing, and internet victimization was also observed Longobardi C et al (78) and may be related to the limited access students have to technology during school hours due to restrictions on mobile phone use.

5.2.2. Sexual Violence

The findings on sexual violence are alarming, with 33% of teachers reporting experiencing some form of sexual harassment from students. This includes obscene remarks, gestures, and stalking. Our results also corroborate with Benbenishty et al (16) who found that 13.6 percent of students in Buea reported the use of obscene remarks against teachers. Although these forms of violence are less frequent compared to psychosocial violence, their impact on the affected teachers' psychological wellbeing and professional efficacy cannot be understated. The cultural context, where discussing sexual harassment is often taboo, may result in underreporting and a potential underestimation of the true prevalence of such incidents.

5.2.3. Physical Violence:

Physical violence was reported by over half of the respondents (52.0%), indicating a severe issue within schools. These results are lower than verbal threats are of a more serious consequence. The prevalence of physical violence observed in our study is similar to the 43.75% obtained by the American Psychological Association Task Force On Violence against Educators (84). The occurrence of such violence suggests a deteriorating respect for authority and a potential spillover of community violence into the school environment. The presence of theft and damage to personal property further underscores the unsafe and volatile environment teachers are navigating.

5.3. Teacher Well-being and School Connectedness

Despite the high prevalence of violence, the data on teacher well-being indicates a resilient teaching force. A significant majority (67.3%) felt that they were effective in their roles, showing a high level of self-efficacy despite the challenges they face. This seems to be in discordance with the findings of Yang and

collaborators who found that the school climate significantly affected teacher's subjective well-being (113). However, the 1.27% of teachers who reported feeling ineffective highlights a group that may be at risk for burnout and professional dissatisfaction.

Similarly, school connectedness data suggests that most teachers (62.5%) feel a sense of belonging and safety at their school, though only 14.1% reported feeling this almost always compared to 20.1% who reportedly felt effective in their roles. This discrepancy could be a further signal the resilient nature of teachers who cope despite not always feeling the school is a comfortable place to be at.

All these positive indicators may be linked to the teachers' commitment to their profession and the support systems within their schools, even in the face of adversity. However, the minority of teachers who feel disconnected or unsafe at school are likely those most affected by violence, indicating a need for targeted interventions to support their well-being.

5.4. Attrition and Professional Stability

The relatively low rate of teachers considering changing schools or professions (15% and 12% respectively) suggests that most teachers are committed to their work despite the challenges they face. However this prevalence is significant and should call the attention of the stake holders on the need to act in order to retain high quality work force. Moreover, the 13.3% who considered early retirement due to school violence is concerning. This suggests that while teachers are generally resilient, the chronic exposure to violence and harassment may push some towards early exit from the profession, leading to a potential loss of experienced educators and further strain on the educational system. These findings are similar to findings

by Yang and collaborators who found that the school climate significantly affected teacher's subjective well-being and increased the rate of turnover (113).

CONCLUSION

The study reveals a troubling prevalence of different forms of violence against teachers in secondary schools in Yaounde VII. Psychosocial, sexual, and physical violence are significant concerns that not only impact the immediate safety and well-being of teachers but also have broader implications for the educational environment and teacher retention.

The data on teacher well-being and attrition intentions shows a dichotomy: while many teachers feel effective and connected to their school communities, there is a notable minority who are struggling with the consequences of violence. This suggests that interventions need to be nuanced and targeted, providing robust support for those at risk while reinforcing the resilience and coping mechanisms of the broader teaching community.

It is imperative that the Ministry of Education, in collaboration with other stakeholders, implements comprehensive strategies to address these issues. This could include enhanced training for teachers on managing difficult behaviors, better reporting mechanisms for incidents of violence, and improved school security measures. Further research should focus on understanding the underlying factors contributing to student-perpetrated violence and the long-term effects on teacher well-being and professional trajectories.

RECOMMENDATIONS

Following our study; we made the following proposals

1. RECOMMENDATION FOR TEACHERS

I. Training and Professional Development:

- Engage in workshops and training sessions focused on conflict resolution, classroom management, and de-escalation techniques. This will enhance teachers' skills in managing difficult behaviors and reduce the likelihood of violence escalating.

II. Establish Peer Support Networks:

- Create or join peer support groups within the school to share experiences and coping strategies. This can help reduce the feelings of isolation and provide a platform for mutual support among colleagues.

III. Utilize Reporting Systems:

- Actively use the established reporting mechanisms to document incidents of violence. This will provide data that can be used to advocate for better policies and resources.

IV. Self-Care and Well-being:

- Prioritize personal well-being through stress management techniques such as mindfulness, physical activity, and seeking professional counseling if needed. This is crucial for maintaining mental and emotional health in a challenging work environment.

2. RECOMMENDATIONS FOR SCHOOL AUTHORITIES

I. Develop and Implement a Violence Prevention Policy:

- Establish clear policies and procedures for preventing and managing violence in schools. This should include guidelines on how to handle incidents, support victims, and disciplinary measures for perpetrators.

II. Enhance School Security:

- Invest in security infrastructure such as surveillance cameras, security personnel, and secure entry points to create a safer school environment. Regularly review and update security measures based on emerging threats.

III. Promote a Positive School Climate:

- Foster a school culture that promotes respect, inclusiveness, and open communication. Encourage activities and programs that build positive student-teacher relationships and reduce the likelihood of conflict.

IV. Support for Affected Teachers:

- Provide access to professional counseling and support services for teachers affected by violence. Establish confidential reporting systems and ensure that victims receive appropriate support and follow-up.

3. RECOMMENDATIONS FOR THE MINISTRY OF EDUCATION

I. Policy and Legislation:

- Develop comprehensive national policies to address school violence, including specific protections for teachers. This should include provisions for mandatory reporting, victim support, and rehabilitation for offending students.

II. Teacher Training and Professional Development:

- Integrate modules on violence prevention, conflict management, and mental health support into teacher training curricula. Ensure that all teachers receive ongoing professional development in these areas.

III. Research and Data Collection:

- Fund and support regular research on school violence to monitor trends and the effectiveness of interventions. Develop a centralized database

for tracking incidents of violence in schools to inform policy and resource allocation.

IV. Collaboration with Stakeholders:

- Collaborate with law enforcement, social services, and community organizations to address the root causes of student violence, such as family issues, substance abuse, and social influences.

4. RECOMMENDATIONS FOR RESEARCHERS

I. Further Study on Root Causes:

- Conduct in-depth research into the underlying factors contributing to student-perpetrated violence against teachers. Focus on socio-economic, cultural, and psychological determinants to develop targeted interventions. Consider a qualitative approach for better understanding of the phenomenon.

II. Longitudinal Studies:

- Implement longitudinal studies to understand the long-term impact of school violence on teachers' career satisfaction, mental health, and retention. This will help in designing effective long-term support strategies.

III. Evaluation of Interventions:

- Assess the effectiveness of existing interventions aimed at reducing school violence. This could include evaluating the impact of teacher training programs, security measures, and support systems on the prevalence of violence.

IV. Develop Tools for Assessing Teacher Well-being:

- Create and validate specific tools for assessing the well-being and resilience of teachers in violent school environments. This will aid in identifying those most at risk and tailoring interventions accordingly.

These recommendations aim to create a safer, more supportive environment for teachers, enhancing their ability to educate effectively while maintaining their well-being and professional satisfaction.

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APPENDIX

Appendix 1: Questionnaire Consent form

Dear Teacher or Administrator,

This survey is being carried out to take a serious look at the growing phenomenon of violence at school, particularly violence directed by students on teachers. We seek to evaluate the prevalence and the consequence of this violence on your work well being. Lastly we intend to appraise your perception of the barrier measures in place.

Why is the survey important to you?

Without your participation, studies such as this will be impossible to conduct. Your data and input will help provide understanding of the problem and help craft informed policies to address the problem.

What will be done with the information provided?

Statistical analysis will be conducted and information gathered will be analysed

Will my information be kept confidential?

Personal information is not being requested so your confidentiality is secured.

Will I be able to assess result at the end of the study?

Yes, the results of the study will be made available to every participating school.

Who else I participating or interested in this survery?

The Ministry of Secondary education is interested in this survery and encourages you to participate. Several researchers, teachers and parents have expressed interest in the findings.

Please sign below to express your informed consent.

Signature _____ Initials of Name _____

Thanks for your time and cooperation.

Contacts of researcher

Dr Tembei Christian Afuh: 000 237 6 76 36 10 85

Spervised by:

Dr Mbei Sosthene

Pr Felicien Ntone

Faculty of Medicine and Biomedical Sciences (Ex CUSS)

QUESTIONNAIRE CONSENT FORM

I [respondents name] _____
hereby give my permission to Dr T. C Afuh (Researcher) to allow me to respond to a questionnaire and to use my responses for academic purposes.

I understand that the research title is **‘Teachers Experiences of Work Place Violence and Harassment committed by learners in public secondary schools in Yaounde.’**

I understand that my participation is voluntary and can be withdrawn anytime.

I understand that in case I feel distressed, I can speak to the counsellor.

I understand the information gathered from this study shall be used to propose solutions to curb teacher directed violence at school.

I also understand that the researcher, hereby named Dr T. C. Afuh, will maintain my anonymity with regards to my responses to the questionnaire items.

I hereby give my permission in the form of my signature below:

Signature _____ Date _____

Contacts of researcher

Dr Tembei Christian Afuh: 000 237 6 76 36 10 85

Spervised by:

Dr Mbei Sosthene

Pr Felicien Ntone

Faculty of Medicine and Biomedical Sciences (Ex CUSS)

Appendix 2: Questionnaire

SECTION 1 SOCIODEMOGRAPHIC AND PHYSICAL PARAMETERS <i>PRAMETRES SOCIODEMOGRAPHIQUE ET PHYSIQUES</i>		
1	Please indicate your Gender <i>Svp veuillez choisir votre genre</i>	Male <input type="checkbox"/> Female <input type="checkbox"/>
2	Please indicate your age <i>SVP veuillez choisir votre age</i>	20-30 <input type="checkbox"/> 31-40 <input type="checkbox"/> 41-50 <input type="checkbox"/> 51-60 <input type="checkbox"/>
3	Please indicate your first official language <i>SVP indiquer votre première langue officielle</i>	English <input type="checkbox"/> French <input type="checkbox"/>
4	Please indicate your responsibility <i>SVP indiquer votre responsabilite</i>	Principal/ <i>Provisieur</i> <input type="checkbox"/> Vice Principal / <i>Vice Provisieur</i> <input type="checkbox"/> Discipline Master / <i>Censeur</i> <input type="checkbox"/> Class master / <i>Maitre de salle</i> <input type="checkbox"/> Counsellor / <i>Conseiller</i> <i>deduction</i> <input type="checkbox"/> Class teacher/ <i>Enseignant</i> <i>Simple</i> <input type="checkbox"/> Other / <i>Autres</i> <input type="checkbox"/> _____
5	Please indicate your number of years working experience <i>SVP indiquer votre nombre(s) d'année d'expérience professionnel</i>	Less than 5 years <input type="checkbox"/> 5-10 years' experience <input type="checkbox"/> 15-15 years' experience <input type="checkbox"/> Greater than 15 years' experience <input type="checkbox"/>
6	Please indicate the number of years working in this school	1 - 3 Years <input type="checkbox"/>

	<i>SVP indiquer le nombre d'années d'exercice dans cette école</i>	4 - 6 Years <input type="checkbox"/> 6 - 9 Years <input type="checkbox"/> > 10 years <input type="checkbox"/>
7	Please indicate your religion <i>SVP indiquer votre religion</i>	Christian <input type="checkbox"/> Muslim <input type="checkbox"/> Buddhist <input type="checkbox"/> Atheist <input type="checkbox"/> Other <input type="checkbox"/>

SECTION 2: EVALUATION OF THE PREVALENCE OF AND THE TYPE OF VIOLENCE COMMITTED BY LEARNERS ON TEACHERS IN THE LAST YEAR

EVALUATION DE LA PREVALENCE ET DU TYPE DE VIOLENCE COMMIS PAR LE LEVE EN VERS L'ENSEIGNANT DURANT LA PRECEDANTE ANNEE

As it pertains to this study, violence directed towards teachers is considered as any act that is committed by the student that makes the school environment unsafe. Below are some questions about your experiences regarding violence in the past year. Please tick the corresponding response.

Dans le cadre de cette étude, la violence dirigée contre les enseignants est considérée comme tout acte commis par l'élève qui rend l'environnement scolaire dangereux. Vous trouverez ci-dessous quelques questions sur vos expériences en matière de violence au cours de la dernière année. Veuillez cocher la réponse correspondante.

Response options;	Never	Almost Never	Sometimes	Often
Very Often				
Options de réponse ;	Jamais	Presque jamais	Parfois	
Souvent Très souvent				

		NEVER	ALMOST NEVER	SOMETIMES	FAIRLY OFTEN	VERY OFTEN
14	In the last year, concerning psychosocial violence by learners , how often have you experienced or witnessed ; <i>Au cours de la dernière année, concernant la violence psychosociale de la part des apprenants, à quelle fréquence avez-vous été victime ou témoin</i>					
	Verbal Threats/ <i>Menaces verbales</i>					

	Intimidation					
	Bullying/ <i>Intimidation par l'élève</i>					
	Mobbing/ <i>Harcèlement</i>					
	Internet/Social Media victimization/ <i>Victimisation sur Internet/réseaux sociaux</i>					
	In the last year, concerning sexual violence by learners , how often have you witnessed or experienced <i>Au cours de la dernière année, concernant les violences sexuelles perpétrées par les apprenants, à quelle fréquence avez-vous été témoin ou victime</i>					
	Obscene Remarks/ <i>Remarques obscènes</i>					
	Obscene Gestures/ <i>Gestes obscènes</i>					
	Stalking/ <i>Traque</i>					
	Unwanted Sexual remarks/ <i>Remarques à caractère sexuel indésirables</i>					
	Unwanted Sexual touches/ <i>Touches sexuelles indésirables</i>					
	Rape/ <i>Viol</i>					
15	In the last year, concerning physical violence by learners , how often have you witnessed or experienced; <i>Au cours de la dernière année, concernant la violence physique de la part des apprenants, à quelle fréquence avez-vous été témoin ou victime ;</i>					
	Objects thrown/ <i>Objets lancés</i>					
	Physically attacked (no doctor visit)					

<i>Agressé physiquement (pas de visite chez le médecin)</i>					
Physically attacked (doctor visit) <i>Agressé physiquement (visite chez le médecin)</i>					
Weapon pulled <i>Arme tirée</i>					
Theft of property <i>Vol de propriété</i>					
Damage to personal property <i>Dommages aux biens personnels</i>					

SECTION 3: EVALUATION OF THE CONSEQUENCE OF VIOLENCE BY LEARNERS ON THE TEACHER'S WORK RELATED WELLBEING
ÉVALUATION DES CONSÉQUENCES DE LA VIOLENCE DES APPRENANTS SUR LE BIEN-ÊTRE LIÉ AU TRAVAIL DE L'ENSEIGNANT

Below are some questions about the consequence of violence by learners on your wellbeing in the past year. Please tick the corresponding response
Vous trouverez ci-dessous quelques questions sur les conséquences de la violence de la part des apprenants sur votre bien-être au cours de l'année écoulée. Merci de cocher la réponse correspondante

Response options:		NEVER R/ Jamais	ALMOST NEVER R	SOMETIMES	FAIRLY OFTEN	VERY OFTEN
18	In the last year, considering the level of teacher directed violence in my school, I would say I have felt like I belong at the school <i>Au cours de la dernière année, compte tenu du niveau de violence dirigée contre les enseignants dans mon école, je dirais que j'ai eu le sentiment d'appartenir à l'école.</i>					

19	<p>In the last year, considering the level of teacher directed violence in my school, I would say I feel like I am a successful teacher.</p> <p><i>Au cours de la dernière année, compte tenu du niveau de violence dirigée contre les enseignants dans mon école, je dirais que j'ai le sentiment d'être un bon enseignant.</i></p>					
20	<p>In the last year, considering the level of teacher directed violence in my school, I would say I can really by myself at this school.</p> <p><i>Au cours de la dernière année, compte tenu du niveau de violence dirigée contre les enseignants dans mon école, je dirais que je peux vraiment me débrouiller seul dans cette école.</i></p>					
21	<p>In the last year, considering the level of teacher directed violence in my school, I would say I am good at helping students learning new things</p> <p><i>Au cours de la dernière année, compte tenu du niveau de violence dirigée contre les enseignants dans mon école, je dirais que je suis apte pour aider les élèves à apprendre de nouvelles choses.</i></p>					
22	<p>In the last year, considering the level of teacher directed violence in my school, I would say I feel like people at this school care about me</p>					

23	<p>In the last year, considering the level of teacher directed violence in my school, I would say I have accomplished a lot as a teacher.</p> <p><i>Au cours de la dernière année, compte tenu du niveau de violence dirigée contre les enseignants dans mon école, je dirais que j'ai l'impression que les gens de cette école se soucient de moi.</i></p>					
24	<p>In the last year, considering the level of teacher directed violence in my school, I would say I am treated with respect in this school.</p> <p><i>Au cours de la dernière année, compte tenu du niveau de violence dirigée contre les enseignants dans mon école, je dirais que je suis traité avec respect dans cette école.</i></p>					
25	<p>In the last year, considering the level of teacher directed violence in my school, I would say I feel like I am effective and helpful.</p> <p><i>Au cours de la dernière année, compte tenu du niveau de violence dirigée contre les enseignants dans mon école, je dirais que je me sens efficace et utile.</i></p>					

SECTION 4: EVALUATE APPRAISE THE LEVEL OF THOUGHTS ON ATTRITION
ÉVALUER LE NIVEAU DES RÉFLEXIONS SUR L'ATTRITION

Below are some questions about your thoughts on attrition. Please tick the corresponding response

Vous trouverez ci-dessous quelques questions sur votre opinion sur l'attrition. Merci de cocher la réponse correspondante

Response options; Never Almost Never Sometimes Often Very Often
Options de réponse ; Jamais Presque jamais Parfois Souvent Très souvent

	<p>In the last year, considering the level of teacher directed violence in your school, do you have thoughts of rather changing your school? <i>Au cours de la dernière année, compte tenu du niveau de violence dirigée contre les enseignants dans votre école, avez-vous plutôt pensé à changer d'école ?</i></p>						
	<p>In the last year, considering the level of teacher directed violence in your school, do you have thoughts of rather changing profession? <i>Au cours de la dernière année, compte tenu du niveau de violence dirigée contre les enseignants dans votre école, avez-vous pensé à changer de profession ?</i></p>						
	<p>In the last year, considering the level of teacher directed violence in my school, do you have thoughts of rather retiring early? <i>Au cours de la dernière année, compte tenu du niveau de violence dirigée contre les enseignants dans mon école,</i></p>						

	<i>envisagez-vous plutôt de prendre une retraite anticipée ?</i>						
<p>Thank you for responding to our questions. All questionnaires are confidential and shall be used for research purposes only. <i>Merci d'avoir répondu à nos questions. Tous les questionnaires sont confidentiels et doivent être utilisés uniquement à des fins de recherche.</i></p>							
<p>If you will like to be contacted to discuss further on how school violence has affected you personally and professionally, and also your thoughts on possible solutions, please tick the box below and write your telephone number so the researcher may contact you. <i>Si vous souhaitez être contacté pour discuter plus en détail de la façon dont la violence à l'école vous a affecté personnellement et professionnellement, ainsi que de vos réflexions sur les solutions possibles, veuillez cocher la case ci-dessous et écrire votre numéro de téléphone afin que le chercheur puisse vous contacter.</i></p>							
<p><input type="checkbox"/> I will like to participate further</p>							
<p>Telephone</p>							

Appendix 3: Ethical clearance